

Why Switzerland Needs a Healthy Ocean: Global Interdependence and National Responsibility

Prof. Thomas Frölicher
Climate and Environmental Physics, University of Bern

Prof. Samuel Jaccard
Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Lausanne

with support of: DONA BERTARELLI
PHILANTHROPY

This article should be cited as: Frölicher, T. L., Jaccard, S. (2025). Why Switzerland Needs a Healthy Ocean: Global Interdependence and National Responsibility. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15619510>

The ocean is a shared global common that benefits all humanity, regardless of where we live. Although landlocked, Switzerland is closely connected to the ocean through critical ecosystem services. Covering 71% of the Earth's surface, the ocean regulates the global climate, sustains essential biogeochemical cycles (including carbon, oxygen, and nutrients), and supports biodiversity that underpins food security, medicine, and biotechnology. It also provides renewable energy, critical raw materials, and irreplaceable cultural, educational, and scientific value. All these benefits depend on a healthy and well-governed marine environment.

Switzerland has a critical role to play in advancing global ocean stewardship. This summary outlines key ocean-related services relevant to Switzerland and underscores why ocean health must be a national concern. Yet significant knowledge gaps remain in quantifying Switzerland's dependence on the ocean, highlighting the need for a precautionary approach in policy and decision-making.

Climate and weather regulation

- The ocean absorbs 90% of excess heat from global warming and 25% of human-generated CO₂ emissions, slowing the pace of climate change.
- Switzerland's climate and weather are directly shaped by oceanic conditions, especially in the Mediterranean and North Atlantic, which influence temperature patterns, precipitation, glacier dynamics and seasonal water availability.
- Ocean warming increases atmospheric moisture, intensifying the risk of heavy rainfall, floods, landslides and seasonal water shortages.
- Switzerland's mountain and glaciers form a major watershed for much of Europe, with ocean-sourced snowfall serving as the primary source of replenishment. As these glaciers melt, they do not only feed major rivers but also contribute to global sea-level rise – underscoring the link between the Alpine cryosphere and coastal regions worldwide.
- Climate sensitive sectors such as agriculture, tourism (around 3% of GDP) and hydropower (which supplies about 60% of domestic electricity) are directly influenced by ocean-driven weather and climate patterns.

Biodiversity, ecosystem health and food security

- The ocean is home to over 2 million species and underpins essential planetary functions such as oxygen production and climate regulation.
- Switzerland's rivers flow into the Mediterranean, northeast Atlantic and Baltic Seas, carrying ecological impacts far beyond its borders.
- The country contributes to marine biodiversity conservation through at least 10 out of its 12 cantonal Universities and Federal Institutes of Technology focusing on ocean-related issues, 24 nationally and internationally active NGOs based in Switzerland, and its support for marine protected areas.
- Switzerland imports 97% of its fish and seafood, with one-third of which is farmed. Many farmed species rely on wild-caught fish for feed – often sourced

unsustainably. Currently, an estimated 1 in 10 assessed marine species is at risk of extinction due to human pressures. This threatens the long-term availability, affordability and diversity of seafood for Swiss consumers.

Marine biotechnology, and ocean economy

- Switzerland's pharmaceutical and biotech industries, contributing about 5% of GDP and \$50 billion in exports, often rely on marine-derived compounds for innovation.
- Switzerland's biotech firms hold 4% of global marine genetic patents, reflecting the country's strong position in marine bio-discovery and innovation.
- Swiss-based companies are active in deep-sea mining and related sectors. Nonetheless, Switzerland supports a precautionary moratorium until strong environmental safeguards and scientific evidence are established.
- Switzerland is tightly integrated into the maritime economy, with around 60 Swiss-based shipping companies operating over 900 vessels. This places Switzerland among the top 40 maritime powers worldwide, with MSC (Mediterranean Shipping Company) now surpassing Maersk as the world's largest container shipping line.
- 94% of the volume of goods imported and 92% of goods exported in Switzerland's foreign trade were transported by sea, representing 30% of imports and 17% of exports by value.
- Efficient, predictable and secure sea trade routes are critical to Switzerland's export-driven economy, global commodities trading, and supply chain logistics.

Science, education and Government engagement

- Switzerland is a leading hub for ocean-related science, with global expertise in ocean modeling, paleoceanography, and marine biogeochemistry and ecology.
- Swiss-based researchers now publish over 100 peer-reviewed papers annually on ocean topics, a tenfold increase over the past 25 years.
- The country plays an active role international science and governance, including through the IPCC (with 10 of the 664 authors of the upcoming AR7 report based in Switzerland), World Ocean Assessment, and the UN Ocean Decade.
- The Swiss Maritime Strategy (2023–2027) reflects a growing commitment to integrated and sustainable ocean governance across policy sectors.
- Public interest in marine topics is rising. The first Swiss Ocean Day in 2024 brought together over 150 participants from science, government, NGOs, and the private sector.
- A 2022 survey found 73% of Swiss respondents view ocean plastic pollution a greater threat than plastic in Swiss nature or drinking water.
- Switzerland plays an active role in international institutions such as the UN, International Maritime Organization (IMO), and WTO, and supports key agreements like High Seas Treaty (BBNJ) to promote marine biodiversity protection and sustainable ocean governance.

Conclusion

Ocean's health is not just a coastal concern, it is a global priority with direct implications for Switzerland's economy, climate and innovation. Strengthening Switzerland's role in ocean science, governance, and sustainability is a strategic investment in the planet's future—and our own.